

NOTES

silica gel column using different organic solvents of increasing polarity.

Compound-A was crystallised from methanol and identified as sitosterol by m.p., m.m.p., spectral data and co-chromatography with its authentic sample³.

Compound-B showed a $[M]^+$ in the mass spectrum at m/z 226 in agreement with the formula $C_{11}H_{14}O_5$. Its uv spectrum is characteristic of benzaldehyde derivatives. The bathochromic shift (9 nm) induced in the uv spectrum of the compound on addition of NaOAc to an ethanolic solution as well as on addition of $AlCl_3/HCl$ (30 nm) indicated the presence of a free hydroxyl group at ortho and para positions with respect to the CHO group⁴. It formed a diacetate with acetic anhydride/pyridine at room temperature. Further acetylation of the diacetate in refluxing pyridine resulted in an amorphous triacetate, δ 6.53 (1H, d, J 2.4 Hz, C-5), 7.21 (1H, d, J 2.4 Hz, C-3), 4.56 (2H, s, O- CH_2), 1.32 (3H, s, CH_3), 1.45 (3H, s, CH_3), 9.63 (1H, s, CHO), 2.22 (3H, s, CH_3COOR), 2.40 (3H, s, CH_3COOAr) and 2.34 (3H, s, CH_3COOAr). This showed the presence of a tertiary hydroxyl group. The 1H nmr spectrum of compound-B showed the presence of two aromatic protons of benzaldehyde ring at δ 6.50 (1H, d, J 2.4 Hz, C-5) and 7.20 (1H, d, J 2.4 Hz, C-3) and CHO protons at δ 9.60 (1H, s). The spectrum also displayed signals at δ 4.60 (2H, s, O- CH_2), 1.25 (3H, s, CH_3), 1.40 (3H, s, CH_3) and 2.20 (1H, br, OH) indicating the presence of -O-2'-hydroxyisobutyl side-chain. Compound-B was thus established to be 4,6-dihydroxy-2-O-(2'-hydroxyisobutyl)benzaldehyde. This new compound has been isolated for the first time from any natural source.

Chemical Examination of Roots of

Asparagus racemosus

M. K. PALIWAL*, I. R. SIDDIQUI,

J. SINGH and H. P. TIWARI

Department of Chemistry, University of Allahabad,
Allahabad-211 002

Manuscript received 13 December 1990,
revised 3 July 1991, accepted 17 July 1991

Compound-C, $C_{28}H_{50}O_2$, m.p. 117° , showed ir bands at 1 464, 733 and 715 cm^{-1} , suggested its aliphatic nature. Absorption at $1\ 730\text{ cm}^{-1}$ showed the presence of ester which was supported by the negative test with 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine. The presence of peaks at $2\ 920$ and $2\ 870\text{ cm}^{-1}$ showed the presence of methylene group. The presence of nmr signal at δ 4.04 (2H, t, methylene ester), 0.87 (6H, s, $2 \times CH_3$), 1.25 (46H, brs, methylene) and 2.21 (2H) ppm is due (2H, t, methylene group adjacent to C=O). On hydrolysis compound-C gave undecanol and cetanoic acid and was assigned as undecanyl cetanoate. This structure was further confirmed by mass fragmentation peak at m/z 223 and 201 due to double rearrangement.

Compound-C was thus established as undecanyl cetanoate, $CH_3-(CH_2)_{14}-CH_2-O-CO-(CH_2)_{10}-CH_3$. The odd carbon fatty acid are not

ASPARAGUS racemosus Willd.¹ (Liliaceae) plant roots find use for a number of ailments². We now report the results of chemical examination of the roots of this plant on which no systematic work has been done so far.

The air-dried and crushed roots (5 kg) was extracted with boiling ethanol. The extract was concentrated under reduced pressure and poured into ice-cold water to give water-soluble and water-insoluble fractions. Water-insoluble fraction was successively extracted with hexane, benzene, ether, ethyl acetate and the individual fraction was worked out separately. Benzene fraction was found to contain three compounds which were separated by

known to occur in facts except in one or two cases⁵. This ester is identical to the ester isolated from seeds of *Cassia spectabilis*⁶, but it is reported for the first time for this plant source.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (M.K.P.) is grateful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for the award of a Senior Research Fellowship.

References

1. "The Wealth of Indian Raw Material", CSIR Publication, New Delhi, 1948, Vol. 1, p. 132; K. R. KIRTIKAR and B. D. BASU, "Indian Medicinal Plants", Lalit Mohan Basu, Allahabad, 1933, Vol. 4, p. 2499.
2. A. K. NADKARNI, "Indian Materia Medica", Popular Book Depot, Bombay, 1954, Vol. 1, p. 153; P. V. SHARMA, "Dravyaguna-Vijnana", Chaukhamba Bharati Academy, Varanasi, 1986, Vol. II, p. 562.
3. A. B. SEN and Y. N. SHUKLA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970 **47**, 96.
4. T. J. MABRY and K. R. MARKHAM, "The Systematic Identification of Flavonoids", Springer, Berlin, 1970.
5. R. P. HANSEN, F. B. SHORTLAND and N. J. COOKE, *Biochemistry*, 1964, **58**, 513; R. P. HANSEN, F. B. SHORTLAND and N. J. COOKE, *Nature*, 1954, **39**, 174.
6. M. SINGH and J. SINGH, *Z. Naturforsch., Teil B*, 1984, **39**, 1425.